

**SUPPORTING DATA FOR THE FOLLOWING PAPER PUBLISHED IN THE
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**Increasing levels of calcium salts of palm fatty acids affect production
responses during the immediate postpartum and carryover periods in dairy
cows**

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INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY

Increasing levels of calcium salts of palm fatty acids affect production responses during the immediate postpartum and carryover periods in dairy cows. Our objective was to determine the dose-response effects of feeding a calcium salts of palm fatty acids on nutrient digestibility and production responses of early-lactation dairy cows grazing on tropical pastures and evaluate carryover effects throughout mid and late lactation. Increasing calcium salts of palm fatty acids from 0 to 0.6 kg/d linearly decreased dry matter intake and body weight change and linearly increased the yields of milk and energy corrected milk with a positive carryover effect across mid and late lactation.

Supplemental Table S1. Individual milk FA of cows fed treatment diets (n=40).

Item	CSPF ¹				SEM	Contrasts ²			P-value ³	
	0	0.2	0.4	0.6		Linear	Quadratic	Cubic	Time	Trt×Time
Selected individual FA, g/d										
C4:0	11.9	12.6	13.3	15.0	1.17	<0.01	0.51	0.75	<0.01	0.12
C6:0	11.8	11.7	11.1	11.8	1.04	0.83	0.65	0.64	0.06	0.65
C8:0	8.02	7.62	6.74	6.34	0.56	0.01	0.99	0.65	0.75	0.15
C10:0	19.6	18.8	15.2	15.3	1.44	0.01	0.65	0.45	0.46	0.05
C12:0	23.6	23.3	19.5	18.6	1.60	0.01	0.86	0.42	0.17	0.03
C14:0	81.3	76.7	69.8	67.6	5.19	0.02	0.77	0.70	0.26	0.22
C14:1	6.32	5.23	4.86	4.59	0.53	0.01	0.37	0.76	0.01	0.17
C16:0	224	245	259	288	17.6	<0.01	0.73	0.70	0.53	0.33
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	10.1	10.1	10.5	10.3	1.00	0.82	0.91	0.78	0.15	0.44
C18:0	96.7	102	102	103	9.18	0.62	0.76	0.86	<0.01	0.97
total <i>trans</i> -C18:1	18.9	20.7	22.7	26.8	1.72	<0.01	0.40	0.78	<0.01	0.83
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	189	190	209	231	14.4	<0.01	0.26	0.70	0.01	0.61
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	13.4	14.1	16.8	17.3	1.02	<0.01	0.91	0.22	<0.01	0.31
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11 C18:2	4.72	4.78	5.48	6.01	0.43	<0.01	0.45	0.56	0.84	0.62
Selected individual FA, g/100g										
C4:0	1.54	1.61	1.63	1.65	0.06	0.10	0.55	0.71	<0.01	0.15
C6:0	1.55	1.49	1.37	1.33	0.05	<0.01	0.86	0.43	0.34	0.56
C8:0	1.05	0.98	0.83	0.78	0.04	<0.01	0.87	0.32	0.76	0.71
C10:0	2.59	2.37	1.88	1.70	0.13	<0.01	0.87	0.30	0.41	0.44
C12:0	3.13	2.96	2.43	2.37	0.15	<0.01	0.70	0.19	0.10	0.30
C14:0	10.7	9.76	8.65	8.10	0.25	<0.01	0.42	0.47	<0.01	0.42
C14:1	0.84	0.68	0.60	0.56	0.06	<0.01	0.25	0.82	<0.01	0.26
C16:0	29.0	31.3	32.3	34.0	0.81	<0.01	0.74	0.70	0.01	0.73
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	1.33	1.28	1.27	1.20	0.08	0.18	0.89	0.70	0.02	0.62
C18:0	12.8	12.9	12.6	11.8	0.57	0.20	0.38	0.99	<0.01	0.34
total <i>trans</i> -C18:1	2.47	2.68	2.88	3.11	0.15	<0.01	0.94	0.91	<0.01	0.97
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	24.9	24.6	26.2	27.0	0.84	0.02	0.48	0.44	0.17	0.91
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	1.76	1.85	2.12	2.01	0.09	0.01	0.24	0.14	0.06	0.70
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11 C18:2	0.63	0.66	0.70	0.71	0.06	0.16	0.84	0.82	0.70	0.85

¹ Inclusion of 4 levels of calcium salts of palm fatty acids (CSPF) replacing a corn-based supplement: 1) 0 (0 kg/d), 2) 0.2 (0.2 kg/d), 3) 0.4 (0.4 kg/d), and 4) 0.6 (0.6 kg/d). Each treatment had 10 animals.

² P-values associated with contrasts: (1) the linear effect of increasing CSPF, (2) the quadratic effect of increasing CSPF, and (3) the cubic effect of increasing CSPF.

³ P-values associated with the effects of time and the interaction treatment (CSPF) × time.

Supplemental Figure S1. Body weight change and energy output to body reserves over time during treatment period [n=40]. Inclusion of 4 levels of calcium salts of palm fatty acids (CSPF) replacing a corn-based supplement: 1) 0 (0 kg/d), 2) 0.2 (0.2 kg/d), 3) 0.4 (0.4 kg/d), and 4) 0.6 (0.6 kg/d). Each treatment had 10 animals. Linear (L), quadratic (Q), or cubic (C) effect of increasing CSPF, with tendencies at $*P \leq 0.10$; and significances at $** P \leq 0.05$ and $*** P < 0.01$. Error bars represent SEM.

Supplemental Figure S2. Body condition score over time during treatment period [n=40]. Inclusion of 4 levels of calcium salts of palm fatty acids (CSPF) replacing a corn-based supplement: 1) 0 (0 kg/d), 2) 0.2 (0.2 kg/d), 3) 0.4 (0.4 kg/d), and 4) 0.6 (0.6 kg/d). Each treatment had 10 animals. Linear (L), quadratic (Q), or cubic (C) effect of increasing CSPF, with tendencies at $*P \leq 0.10$; and significances at $** P \leq 0.05$ and $*** P < 0.01$. Error bars represent SEM.